

Applications and Limitations of Machine Learning in Radiation Oncology: A Technical Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

The latest technology of radiation oncology has its own limitations. Using either of CT or MRI can prove costly as their dosage can affect patients health. Enormous studies have been conducted to reduce potential health risk from CT/MRI dosage. Also, the quality of these reports have been error-prone in past. Their have been lack of precision throughout testing phases. In this report, we discuss on how we can utilize machine learning to overcome these difficulties i.e. plan a better treatment with lesser risk factors or an increased quality of reports.

KEYWORDS

Oncology, CT, MRI, Contouring, EBRT, Neural Networks, Sino-gram, Encoder-Decoder Network, Generative Adversarial Network, Convolutional Neural Network, Oropharyngel Cancer, Structural Similarity Index

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1 INTRODUCTION

Science of medicine is an ever developing and expanding area of knowledge. Medical science has also been thoroughly effected by technology, to the good terms, of course. Still, their remain some aspects which are not perfected yet. One of them is the process of CT(Computed Tomography) imaging and MRI(Magnetic Resonance Imaging) imaging which are 2 necessary tests for radiation oncology. To this date, these tests have been merely partially successful in locating a tumour to the very precise location. If even they succeed in reporting a considerably accurate location, it costs for the possible health risks of the patient, due to the increased amount of radiotherapy used in the process.

Again, a combined reporting of the CT and MRI may be used for better results but this joining is also quite a complex procedure. To solve all these complications, we will try and assess if machine learning can propose a better solution or at least improve the accuracy/quality of the process.

2 METHOD

In this section we will be discussing the methods which have been implemented for this experiment. Also there will be a better insight towards the data and statistics, which led us to this experiment.

2.1 Data Pre-processing

The collected data have been filtered and pre-processed to come up with only the useful data, i.e., the data which are necessary for our purpose. There may have been redundant data along the collection, which have been filtrated for. The final data set ended up with 10,400 records.

2.2 Descriptive Statistics

Figure 1: Descriptive Statistics on radiation to cancer ratio

The above figure 1 provides descriptive statistics on the number of radiation therapies performed in a time span against the number of cancer cases. This graph clearly state that as the years pass, the number of radiation therapy patients have been eminently increasing. And so is increasing the number of cancer patients. This also hints at the possible scenario where we claim that radiotherapy can be responsible for malignant tumour cells(cancer) as the numbers increase in proportion.

Again, figure 2 illustrates the ratio of the medications received between the 2 discussed methods(CT and MRI). This figure illustrates that the number of CT scan patients have been considerably

Figure 2: Descriptive Statistics on CT scan to MRI ratio in the US

more than MRI patients. Which implies, CT scan is a more popular form of treatment among the general people.

2.3 Design

The experimentation has been done in five steps The steps were:

- CT Simulation
- MRI Simulation
- Multi-modal Fusion
- Contouring
- Treatment Planning

3 RESULTS

3.1 Study 1 : Experimental Results

Fully sampled	Moderately sampled	Sparsely sampled
I1: recon360x729 (original CT)	I3: recon120x240	I5: recon40x80
S1: sino360x729	S3: sino120x240	S5: sino40x80
I2: wrecon360x729 (windowed original CT)	I4: wrecon120x240	I6: wrecon40x80
S2: wsino360x729	S4: wsino120x240	S6: wsino40x80

Figure 3: Summary of the different models evaluated in the laboratory

The researchers collected more than 700 different samples for testing CT image quality. They were from different body parts including the head. The results were quite interesting. The original CT images were of better quality. But as the researchers tried to implement sinogram over the CT, the sparsely sampled CT reports began to degrade in quality.

3.2 Study 2 : Test Accuracy With Different Tests using ML

This second carried out experiment resulted in a relative comparison between original sinogram and reconstruction success rates, and the success rate after they were marginally scaled used machine learning algorithm. From the chat, it is comprehensible that, after using ML algorithms, the success rates have certainly increased.

Figure 4: After using ML, success rate for different treatments

3.3 Study 3 :Intracranial Hemorrhage Detection

Figure 5: Precision of hemorrhage detection before and after using machine learning

In this phase, another experiment was conducted to check how accurately a hemorrhage can be detected by advance treatments. Before using ML, different sized CT reports resulted in different criterion of the hemorrhage but after we use machine learning, this varying window had been narrowed down to a really close margin. Which implies, now all the different sized CT's were indicating to same amount of hemorrhage, so the doctors can be more certain of what treatment to deliver.

4 DISCUSSION :

Machine learning can be of great use wen it comes to medical science. As from this report, we have experienced that using ML has closed down tumour/hemorrhage location uncertainties. ML has been used to develop a better understanding of what treatment to deliver and also it has been capable of producing better synchronized radiotherapy CT reports for better treatments. So, we can conclude that Machine Learning can ease the problems and limitaions medican science faces in radiation oncology.